

SafeHabitus

**Desk-study to review the
roles and competencies of EU
institutional actors on farm
OSH documents and
interviews and focus groups
with senior EU officials**

Deliverable D6.1

Deliverable description

Deliverable	D6.1 Desk-study to review the roles and competencies of EU institutional actors on farm OSH documents and interviews and focus groups with senior EU officials
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Executive Summary

The governance of agricultural health and safety within the EU is characterised by a complex and often unclear system of oversight. Multiple Directorate-Generals (DGs) and agencies hold responsibility for different aspects of health and safety. This fragmented structure can make it difficult to determine who is accountable for specific areas of policy and implementation.

Deliverable 6.1 aims to provide a clear and accessible mapping of the key institutions and their respective roles in agricultural health and safety governance. It assesses whether the current policies and governance framework are adequate in addressing the sector's needs. Where shortcomings are identified, the report explores potential improvements to enhance coordination, effectiveness, and overall safety for those working in agriculture. Who is responsible for EU policy and governance of agricultural health and safety? Some have responsibility (DGs) while others are advocates (European Federation of Food, Agriculture and Tourism Trade Unions (EFFAT), the Employers' Group of Professional Agricultural Organisations in the European Union (GEOPA)). This deliverable aims to map out, in an accessible way, who has responsibility for what, assess if the current policies and governance framework is adequate, and if not, how it might be improved.

What's the problem?

There is a lack of clarity about policy responsibility for agricultural health and safety; the Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion (DG EMPL) is responsible for workers, but the Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI) has responsibility for Social Conditionality which covers agricultural workers (including seasonal workers), and it is unclear who is responsible for diseases transmitted from animals to people working on farms (such as farmers and veterinarians). Without clarity, it is difficult to see who is accountable for ensuring the health of people working on farms. Responsibilities are complex and shared between different DGs and agencies. It is not clear how effectively there is good governance with coordination and cooperation between these bodies, people interviewed reported poor or no collaboration.

Research Objectives

This deliverable has three main research objectives: 1) to undertake a desk study to identify and review the role and competencies of EU institutional actors responsible for farm Occupational Safety and Health (OSH); 2) to undertake interviews and focus groups with high level policy actors and stakeholder representatives to assess current policy design and delivery and their understanding of their responsibilities for farm OSH; 3) make recommendations for improved policy frameworks at the right level of governance considering the various competencies involved.

Methods

Drawing on expert input and desk-based research, the study commenced by mapping relevant EU OSH institutional actors, stakeholders and social partners engaged with farmers and farm workers at EU level. Relevant policy literature published by these institutions was reviewed including position statements and briefs, EU directives relating to (farm) OSH, legislative and guidance documents and other information on their websites. This provided insight into their roles and competencies and how their work influences OSH in agriculture. The results of the mapping exercise and the review of policy literature supported the completion of a series of focus groups (3) and interviews (8) with representatives from the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA), DG AGRI, DG EMPL, European Foundation for Living and Working Conditions (Eurofound), EFFAT, GEOPA, a Senior Labour Inspector and the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC).

Results

The policy and governance framework at the EU level on farm OSH is complex and fragmented, without any significant collaboration between the key actors. The remit of relevant policy makers and stakeholder agencies at the EU level does not include self-employed workers and their families. This means the main EU OSH policy does not cover 86% of people working on EU farms. While this is recognised as a shortcoming there was little commitment or ability to tackle this issue. Policy makers felt that the lack of data about farm accidents means it is not seen as a policy priority, except in the case of seasonal workers, where there has been high profile coverage in European media. DG AGRI is responsible for the implementation of the Social Conditionality, a new requirement under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023–2027, linking CAP payments to compliance with selected [EU labour and social standards](#). These include EU Occupational Health and Safety Directives (89/391/EEC) and (2009/104/EEC) and the Directive on fair working conditions (Directive 2019/1152 on Transparent and Predictable Working Conditions). The Social Conditionality requirement seeks to improve working conditions and social rights for agricultural workers by ensuring that farmers (employers) who receive direct payments and certain rural development funds adhere to key EU employment laws.

Recommendations

Improve policy governance for farm OSH at the EU level

- **DG EMPL:** DG EMPL should take responsibility for coordinating a cross-DG/agency working group on farm OSH. Given that it is recognised by EU policy makers that there is little coordination between bodies, this will not happen until one entity takes responsibility for coordination.

- **DG EMPL:** In line with Article 16 of the 89/391 framework Directive¹, DG EMPL should propose, as was originally foreseen, an individual OSH Directive on Agriculture. This Directive should include self-employed workers. This would provide an in-depth and wide-ranging overview of the OSH needs of all farm workers including the self-employed. It could also provide an overview of the regulatory and legislative changes required at an EU level to ensure all relevant bodies have responsibility for self-employed farm workers in their remit. It should also include an in-depth study of the needs of pregnant women regarding contact with animals and pesticides.
- **EFFAT, GEOPA, the Committee of Professional Agricultural Organisations and the General Confederation of Agricultural Cooperatives (COPA-COGECA), the European Council of Young Farmers (CEJA):** Until regulatory change happens the social partners will continue to be EFFAT and GEOPA, omitting self-employed workers. Before this is achieved, EFFAT and GEOPA should work closely with COPA-COGECA and CEJA to ensure representation of self-employed farm workers. GEOPA and EFFAT hope to develop an insurance scheme that will compensate farm employers and employees for lost income due to climate change. They intend to use the Parity Funds at their disposal to avoid private insurance that will charge high premiums. It is essential that such an insurance scheme is also inclusive of self-employed farmers.
- **COPA-COGECA** should use its lobbying power to raise the need for health and safety of self-employed workers to be an EU policy priority.
- **Member States** should ratify the International Labour Organisation (ILO) Convention C184 on OSH in Agriculture and implement the measures of its supplementary Recommendation 192 (which includes the self-employed). This convention, if adopted by all Member States along with the measures of its supplementary Recommendation 192, would de facto serve as a European Directive on OSH and working conditions in agriculture. A similar approach has been successfully taken up by the EU Council of Ministers and EU Social Partners in the fisheries sector.

Improve quality data about farm accidents to ensure farm OSH is a policy priority:

- **DG EMPL** should propose a directive on OSH in agriculture that should address the issue of standardising inspection practices and requirements across the Member States. This can be implemented by the European Labour Authority and the EU Senior Labour Inspectors' Committee (SLIC) and would both improve the quality of information, and level an unfair playing field that currently exists; at present some Member States carry out compulsory farm inspections, while in other Member States, farm inspection of self-employed farmers is not compulsory.

¹ The EC should act in line with Article 16 of the [original Directive 89/391](#) and “adopt” an individual Directive on “agriculture”, the only individual Directive not realised in the framework Directive. Even fisheries has its own individual OSH Directive

- To improve the quality, consistency, and comparability of data on farm-related fatalities—including deaths by suicide—Eurostat should establish a dedicated working group on coronial and medico-legal death data. This group should bring together representatives from national statistical offices, coroners' services, public health authorities, and relevant agricultural and labour bodies. The working group should:
 - Focus specifically on improving the classification, recording, and reporting of unnatural deaths in the agricultural sector, including suicides among farmers and farm family members.
 - Identify best practices and common standards for collecting and coding coronial data across Member States, considering the unique circumstances of farm-related deaths.
 - Develop guidelines to support more granular, sector-specific analysis of mortality data in agriculture, and ensure that this information feeds into EU-level health, safety, and social sustainability indicators.

This initiative should be aligned with ongoing efforts under the Farm Sustainability Data Network and supported by the European Commission in coordination with relevant DGs, including DG EMPL, DG AGRI, and Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE).

- DG EMPL/ EU-OSHA/ DG Sante/ Eurofound: More data is needed on the risks posed by pesticides and animal disease to pregnant and breastfeeding women. More data in general is needed about health and safety risks for women.

Governance of Social Conditionality:

- **DG EMPL and DG AGRI:** Social Conditionality should be DG EMPL's responsibility as the responsible DG for worker health and safety and labour conditions. Social Conditionality should be developed progressively in tandem with the proposal of an OSH Directive in Agriculture by DG EMPL. Until this happens, DG EMPL and DG AGRI should coordinate more effectively on their policies. DG AGRI should consider its role in ensuring implementation of Social Conditionality by implementing similar measures to cross-compliance.

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Introduction

Ensuring occupational safety and health (OSH) in agriculture especially on the farm remains a high priority in the EU. Studies² have shown that the agricultural sector is still among the high-risk sectors in the EU when OSH is considered. Both farm employers and employees now have to operate in a world of work that is changing with even more dynamic OSH needs in order to keep up with the food and nutritional needs of the EU. To better protect workers from work-related accidents and diseases, the European Commission adopted several strategic documents including the EU strategic framework on health and safety at work. The most recent 2021-2027 EU strategic framework on health and safety at work builds on previous frameworks and lessons learnt from different stakeholder consultations and OSH experiences and has three main objectives³:

1. Anticipating and managing change in the new world of work brought about by the green, digital and demographic transitions.
2. Improving prevention of workplace accidents and illnesses.
3. Increasing preparedness for any potential future health crises.

The strategic framework promotes a 'vision zero' approach to work-related deaths with also a target to safeguard all workers as reflected in the European Pillar of Social Rights. Also, for the first time, the new Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) introduced a Social Conditionality⁴ aspect that seeks to ensure on-farm safety and health as well as transparent and predictable employment and labour conditions for farm employees in the EU. Social Conditionality was also adopted based on consultations with different stakeholders with the expectation that Member States will work to ensure implementation and compliance. There are two significant limitations of Social Conditionality. Firstly, it only applies to paid farm employees and does not impact self-employed farmers and their families, accounting for 86% of the farm workforce⁵. Secondly, it only applies to the direct payments schemes of the CAP and therefore excludes key labour-intensive sectors, such as horticulture, olive and wine sectors, where the majority of workers are seasonal and migrant workers. As such, the roles that stakeholders including social partners play in ensuring that farm employers and workers have the right information, support and policies to promote occupational safety and health in the EU cannot be overemphasized. Several EU institutions and stakeholders work to provide policy support, information and inspection to enable farmers, farm employers and workers meet the requirements for OSH and reduce the risks posed to them. Thus, understanding how stakeholders' roles and competencies are utilised to inform OSH

2 See https://osha.europa.eu/sites/default/files/Review_%20future_Agriculture_OSH.pdf and https://osha.europa.eu/sites/default/files/Risk_assessment_upper_limbs_agriculture_INAIL.pdf

3 See <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021DC0323&qid=1626089672913#PP1Contents>

4 See https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/cap-overview/cap-2023-27/key-reforms-new-cap_en

5 See https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Agriculture_statistics_-_family_farming_in_the_EU

policies, directives as well as practices among farmers and farm employees remains crucial to understanding and improving the policy support framework available to help foster farm OSH at the EU level and in EU Member States.

Against this background, the aim of this desk study is to review the roles and competencies of EU institutional actors and stakeholders as it relates to farm OSH. First, EU institutions, stakeholders and social partners that are relevant for farm OSH were identified. Second, their roles and competencies in relation to farm OSH are presented. Third, a review of how these roles and competencies foster stakeholder connections that impact farm OSH are presented.

Findings from the desk review suggests organised collaborations in general between EU OSH institutions and EU agencies, social partners and other relevant stakeholders. Three types of stakeholders were identified based on their roles and competencies namely, **oversight, support, and social/representation**. Oversight stakeholders are the main decision and policy makers backed by EU legislative power. OSH support stakeholders provide information, implementation or advise depending on their mandates. Social/representation stakeholders represent farmers, farm employees and employers. Each have varying degree of power to influence OSH outcome at the EU level. All the stakeholders identified provide information on OSH for farm employers and employees with the majority of them working to achieve their OSH obligations using different approaches as stipulated in their action plans. Most stakeholders aim to avoid duplicity of efforts as they collaborate, and they do so with some degree of success. Yet, they all work as information stakeholders as part of their roles. They use both scientific and social expertise to delve into OSH issues across the EU institutions in line with their roles and competencies.

The OSH framework directive⁶ and most of the other 24 EU directives⁷ on OSH set the minimum standards for safety and health that applies directly to all workers in agriculture but does not cover the self-employed. Each have been developed with some updated to cover new and emerging health and safety risks. Stakeholders involved in OSH in agriculture generally agree that they are still relevant and sufficient for ensuring OSH and will continue to update them to cover areas or risks when needed. Where there seems to be a disconnect is that despite the broad range of OSH directives that covers OSH issues encountered in agriculture and the relatively high level of collaboration and information exchange between relevant OSH stakeholders, there are still high levels of accidents, fatalities and OSH infringement in agriculture in the EU. Because EU level OSH institutions and agencies tend to deal with all sectors (with the exception of DG AGRI that works specifically on agriculture), sector-specific progress or challenges are difficult to track from just the annual reports that these institutions publish except when they produce reports and information on OSH issues in agriculture. As such OSH information and stakeholder connections do not guarantee higher level of compliance to ensure that OSH risks are sufficiently minimised or completely prevented at farm level.

The EU-OSHA provides very comprehensive research and information on EU OSH including but not limited to OSH traditional, new and emerging risks as well as links to OSH directives

6 See <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A31989L0391&qid=1615985898418>

7 See <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=148&langId=en> for other EU OSH Legislation

and labour laws. As an agency of the DG EMPL, it is well positioned to inform policy and practice for farm OSH especially with the introduction of Online interactive Risk Assessment (OiRA) developed in collaboration with the EU social partners in agriculture to help farmers do free online risk assessments for OSH. It was hoped that the introduction of the Social Conditionality for working conditions and on-farm OSH in the CAP strategic plans would lead to potential for collaboration both at the EU and national levels. However, most Member States reported that setting up Social Conditionality may be complex. As a result, Member States were given until January 1st, 2025, to put the new conditionality into effect. Only France, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg, Spain, and Portugal implemented it prior to this date. Consequently, we will need to wait until at least 2026 to conduct a comprehensive impact assessment on the practical implementation of conditionality across the EU. It is not clear how the DG Agri plans to work with the EU-OSHA in ensuring that the Social Conditionality benefits from the EU-OSHA's expertise. The inclusion of the Social Conditionality calls for new ways of supporting the variety of farmers that benefit from the CAP to ensure OSH beyond withholding CAP payment for non-compliance.

The EuroFound and Eurostat as well as the EU-OSHA through their European Survey of Enterprises on New and Emerging Risks (ESENER) provide a variety of OSH data that informs not just research, but also policy. The data collected are mainly on risks, accidents, non-compliance, barriers and other challenges faced with OSH, however coverage on good practices and OSH successes especially in agriculture are rarely considered. This is also the case for the collection and use of qualitative data that could provide in depth insight into some of the OSH issues that is not captured quantitatively.

The EU social partners in agriculture EFFAT and GEOPA-COPA work both individually and together to ensure that their positions on agricultural policies and legislations including on farm OSH are communicated through continuous dialogue with decision-makers. Their campaigns and information also showcase several OSH issues that affect the members that they represent as well as a knowledge and information system to ensure workers know their rights. EFFAT and GEOPA are currently working together to safeguard employees and employers against loss of income due to climate change. Although the CEJA represents the young in agriculture and have been involved in other partnerships to enhance OSH among its members, it is not clear how and whether they cooperate with the social partners especially the EFFAT that also have a youth and women's committee as part of its structure. There is potential for better cooperation since they all represent farmers, farm workers and farm employers.

Finally, the CAP seeks to improve generational renewal and women's participation in agriculture. The CAP also seeks to include smaller farmers. The policy and practical implications of these commitments need to be considered by OSH EU institutions and stakeholders. This calls for OSH stakeholder connections that are established to deal specifically with OSH issues in agriculture and on the farm. Stakeholders especially the social partners need to critically consider how OSH risks affect these group of farmers and farm workers and how through their collaborations with other EU institutions they can proffer sustainable OSH solutions to the challenges that they face. Also, given the rapidly changing ways of work, the need for decision-makers and other stakeholders to think critically on how more specialised social data can be collated, analysed and disseminated to help improve farm OSH is crucial.

Method

This study first identified relevant OSH EU institutional actors, stakeholders and social partners engaged with farmers and farm workers at EU level. The institutional actors and stakeholders identified include:

- Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs & Inclusion (DG EMPL) and its dependent committees: Advisory Committee for Safety and Health at Work (ACSH) and Senior Labour Inspectors Committee (SLIC)
- European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA)
- European Labour Authority (ELA)
- European Foundation for Living and Working Conditions (Eurofound)
- Directorate-General Agriculture and Rural Development (DG-AGRI)
- European Commission Eurostat
- Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (DG Sante)
- European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)
- European Parliament Committees: The European Parliament's Committee on Agriculture (AGRI), the European Parliament Committee on Employment and Social Affairs (EP EMPL) and the Committee on Women's Rights and Gender Equality (FEMM)
- The European Economic and Social Committee (EESC)
- European Committee of the Regions (CoR)
- EU CAP Network
- European Federation of Food, Agriculture, and Tourism Trade Unions (EFFAT)
- The Committee of Professional Agricultural Organisations and the General Confederation of Agricultural Cooperatives (COPA-COGECA)
- The European Council of Young Farmers (CEJA)
- International Labour Organisation (ILO), the Food and Agricultural Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) and International Section of the ISSA on Prevention in Agriculture

Once these institutional actors and stakeholders were identified, their strategic documents action plans, mission statements, publications on farm OSH specifically and other OSH issues as well as position statements and briefs, EU directives relating to farm OSH, legislative and guidance documents and other relevant information on their websites were reviewed. This provided insight into their roles and competencies as actors and how their work influence OSH in agriculture.

Roles and Competencies of EU Institutions, Committees, Social Partners and Organisations toward Farm OSH

EU Institutions and Agencies

Directorate-General Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion (DG EMPL)

The Directorate-General Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion (DG EMPL) is the EU Commission department responsible for EU policy on employment, social affairs, skills and labour mobility. Apart from working to promote high level of employment in the EU amongst other roles as enshrined in the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), the DG EMPL plays a critical role in developing and promoting policies, knowledge exchange and legislative and non-legislative guidance to ensure OSH in all sectors including agriculture in the EU. This entails providing both oversight function on OSH in all sectors and working to ensure decent and safe working conditions for all by promoting access to information as well as implementation, enforcement and updating of OSH directives including those that apply to workers and employers in the agricultural sector in all Member States. DG EMPL does not have responsibility for self-employed workers. The DG EMPL also monitors claims on infringement of workers' rights and works through exchanges in the Senior Labour Inspectors Committee (SLIC) and Advisory Committee on Safety and Health at Work (ACSH) and the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA). As decentralised agencies of the EU, the EU-OSHA alongside the European Labour Authority (ELA), the European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions (Eurofound) play diverse yet complementary roles on OSH and working conditions issues in all sectors across the EU.

In line with the strategic frameworks on EU OSH, the Commission works in consultation with social partners and national authorities in Member States to update EU OSH directives, address OSH risks and contribute to social dialogues on sector-specific OSH needs. The DG EMPL also provides policy support, evaluation and impact assessments of social and labour market issues. For instance, the DG EMPL also recently published two reports launched by the European Commission on mobile seasonal workers and intra-EU labour mobility and a study on the effectiveness of policies to tackle undeclared work. These studies show that seasonal and undeclared work remain high in the agricultural sector and highlight some of the challenges related to seasonal work that still affect OSH and employment conditions as well as reviewing policies used to tackle undeclared work in the EU.

European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA)

The European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA) is the EU's information agency⁸ responsible for occupational safety and health across all sectors. It does not have responsibility for self-employed workers. The EU-OSHA plays a significant role and is situated

⁸ See <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32019R0126#d1e290-58-1> for their founding regulation

to help facilitate the European Commission's strategic framework and priorities for OSH using a tripartite approach involving employers, employees and government (both EU and national). The EU-OSHA provides access to relevant OSH facts and figures, advice at EU level and national OSH legislations as well as EU guidelines, standards and OSH strategies.

Apart from the support provided for OSH in the EU in line with the strategic framework⁹, the EU-OSHA runs the healthy workplaces campaigns¹⁰ to raise awareness about workplace OSH risks and how to prevent them. These campaigns have been running since 2000 with a recent (2023-2025) campaign on safety and health in the digital age. The campaign places OSH within the EU policy debate in line with the objectives of European Digital Strategy and the 'vision zero' approach to work-related deaths. The campaign¹¹ places emphasis on small and medium-sized enterprises and works through a network of national focal points, official campaign partners, media, social partners and intermediaries to reach out to businesses across the EU. The EU-OSHA has also commissioned several research publications by different authors and institutions with expertise in OSH that directly and in some cases indirectly assess current and emerging OSH issues and risks¹² in agriculture. The information from these publications remains crucial for informing farm OSH policies and farm employers.

Conducting the European Survey of Enterprises on New and Emerging Risks (ESENER) is also one of the main competencies of the EU-OSHA. The survey has been done every five years since 2009. Businesses and organisations are asked to respond to the EU-OSHA questionnaire on the nature of the general safety and health risks that they face and how they are managed. This also presents a feedback system where businesses and organisations across the EU can give details on the different risks that they face and how their workers participate in health and safety practices. The EU-OSHA also runs the OSHwiki¹³ – an online encyclopaedia that provides both generic and sector-specific (including agriculture) information on OSH across different themes as well as access to an independent, peer reviewed scientific journal called Safety Science Monitor.

Other roles that the EU-OSHA play are the foresight projects and OSH overviews. Together these are used to gather and analyse data to provide information on new technologies and new ways of working to identify emerging risks and inform OSH priority areas to meet the health and safety needs of EU workers. The EU-OSHA uses the Napo films¹⁴ in collaboration with some OSH-related organisations in the EU using language-free films to demonstrate some OSH issues and risks to different audiences.

The EU-OSHA also developed an Online interactive Risk Assessment (OiRA) for agriculture with input and collaboration with the EU Social Partners; GEOPA and EFFAT. This allows employers in agriculture, forestry and fishing do free risk assessment to help tackle the OSH

9 See <https://osha.europa.eu/sites/default/files/EU-OSHA%20strategy%202022-2027.pdf>

10 These campaigns are considered the largest of their kind in the world

11 See <https://healthy-workplaces.osha.europa.eu/en> for details

12 See <https://osha.europa.eu/en/publications> for details

13 See <https://oshwiki.osha.europa.eu/en> for details

14 See <https://osha.europa.eu/en/tools-and-resources/napo-safety-smile> for details

challenges that they face. It also provides links to information to help farmers access legal and policy documents on OSH. The risk assessment gives comprehensive information on OSH risk assessment. It is also generic and lengthy and may not help farmers meet farm and sector-specific OSH needs especially for those on small farms and self-employed farmers who constitute the majority of the European farm labour force.

Advisory Committee on Safety and Health at Work (ACSH)

The Advisory Committee on Safety and Health at Work (ACSH) is a tripartite body set up by a council decision 2003/C 218/01 in 2003¹⁵. The ACSH is composed of 3 full members from national governments in Member States, trade unions across sectors and employers' organisations as well as 3 interest groups that represents them and 2 alternate members appointed to each full member. It works through several Working Parties (WPs) on specific technical issues to help prepare draft opinions. The main role of the ACSH is to assist the Commission in the preparation, implementation and evaluation of activities in OSH and facilitates cooperation between national administrations, trade unions and employers' organisations. It performs this role by giving its opinions on EU OSH initiatives and legislations, identifying priority areas for OSH and supporting the exchange of views and experiences between stakeholders and Member States at EU and national levels and publishes an annual report¹⁶ of its meetings and Working Parties. The ACSH's action programme for 2021-2027¹⁷ is tailored to support the objectives in the EU strategic framework OSH and is revised annually as OSH needs evolve. The ACSH also works in cooperation with other EU agencies, committees and international agencies such as the EU-OSHA, Eurofound and Eurostat, European Chemical Agency, Committee of Senior Labour Inspectors (SLIC) and the ILO.

Senior Labour Inspectors Committee (SLIC)

The Senior Labour Inspectors Committee (SLIC)¹⁸ gives an opinion on all matters relating to the enforcement of EU legislation on health and safety at work in Member States. The principal roles of the SLIC include defining the common principles of labour inspection and developing methods of assessing national systems of inspection. It also promotes information exchange, knowledge and mutual understanding for the different national systems and practices of labour inspection as well as studying the possible impact of other community policies on labour inspection activities on OSH. The Work Plan¹⁹ for SLIC is developed to complement the key priorities of the EU OSH framework 2021-2027. This includes strengthening of OSH enforcement principles, identifying the impact of new,

15 See <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=148&intPagId=683&langId=en&>

16 See https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/cb9293be-4563-4f19-89cf-4c4588bd6541/library/9ec27d87-5d28-4542-b01c-1e2664c2d45d?p=1&n=10&sort=modified_DESC

17 See <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/cb9293be-4563-4f19-89cf-4c4588bd6541/library/8a02f835-2465-4ba7-a180-3268072109d2/details>

18 Although the SLIC started to meet informally in 1982, it was given a formal status by the Commission Decision 95/319/EC which was amended in 2008 (2008/823/EC)

19 See <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/fea534f4-2590-4490-bca6-504782b47c79/library/ce16199c-4eea-4cc4-ac9c-5216dc983c2d/details>

emerging and traditional risks, addressing the challenges that comes with new forms of work, knowledge exchange as well as communication and cooperation with EU and international agencies – ACSH, EU-OSHA, ELA, the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) and ILO²⁰. Several Working Groups and Specific Working Groups support the work of SLIC. For example, the Specific Working Group of enforcement of EU OSH for Mobile Workers deals OSH issues relating to seasonal, migrant, mobile, short-time contract workers or the Specific Working Group EMEX which assesses Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs) and psychosocial risks common to the agricultural sector.

European Labour Authority (ELA)

The European Labour Authority works to ensure that the EU rules on labour mobility and social security coordination are adhered to effectively and fairly. ELA partners with different EU agencies and social partners like the EFFAT (who champion rights for seasonal workers), to achieve these through information exchange (campaigns, capacity building, workshops and seminar) involvement in concerted and joint inspections and tackling undeclared work across different sectors. The single programming document²¹ for 2023-2025 shows ELA's commitment to engage with and support Member States and social partners in achieving the CAP's Social Conditionality especially since the agricultural sector attract a high proportion of seasonal workers who are usually also mobile workers. ELA has also shown commitment to cooperate with the EU-OSHA to ensure that OSH requirements are met for workers considered to be vulnerable²². Through working groups such as the European Platform tackling undeclared work established in 2021, the ELA also supports Member States in tackling undeclared work in agriculture²³. ELA's concerted and joint inspections²⁴ in 2022 revealed concerns among some workers in agriculture (forestry, horticulture and vineyards) and the meat industry. However, the report did not give details on what these concerns were. Details on gender were also not included. The focus is on more agri-industry and large-scale agriculture with less of a focus on smaller farms, which is the norm in the EU. Also, it is not clear how the ELA plans to support Social Conditionality since OSH is not in their mandate.

The European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions (Eurofound)

Eurofound provides information, advice, knowledge and expertise to support the development of better-informed social, employment and work-related policies. It does so through research, survey data collection and analysis of working conditions, industrial relations, employment, labour markets and living conditions to inform policy and guide

20 See <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/fea534f4-2590-4490-bca6-504782b47c79/library/59de9da0-5102-4f1f-8862-af64c899a327/details>

21 See <https://www.ela.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2023-02/ELA-Single-Programming-Document-2023-2025-2.pdf>

22 Seasonal and posted workers

23 See https://www.ela.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2023-06/Platform-Work-Plan_2023-and-suggestions-for-2024-2025.pdf for European Platform tackling undeclared work: Work Plan 2023 and proposals for 2024-2025

24 <https://www.ela.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2023-07/ela-consolidated-annual-activity-report-2022.pdf>

different stakeholders' policy actions. The agency collaborates with the EU-OSHA²⁵ on OSH and living conditions data across the EU with both agencies contributing to knowledge and information on working conditions and OSH. The Eurofound also conducts three pan-European surveys – European Company Survey, European Quality of Life Survey and European Working Conditions survey²⁶. Together these provide crucial data for Eurofound's work and for the stakeholders and EU social partners that they work with. The European Company surveys entail surveys of businesses with at least 10 employees. This implies that businesses, especially farms with less than 10 employees may be left out in the European Company surveys and subsequently policies that are informed by these surveys may not cater to the needs of those businesses. The European Working Conditions survey which entails both quantitative and qualitative analysis will investigate psychosocial risks and associated working conditions (in collaboration with the EU-OSHA) as well as the challenges of being self-employed across different sectors, occupation, age and gender²⁷. These and other analysis continue to provide valuable information that is useful for OSH stakeholders decision-making. For example, a report²⁸ on the working conditions and job quality in the agricultural sector by Eurofound shows among other findings lower awareness of OSH risks compared to other sectors as well as lower mental well-being, higher health problems and lower absenteeism when compared to other sectors. More recently Eurostat have issued a report on climate change which includes a focus on agriculture, not just in terms of outdoor work in excessive heat, but also the health implications of an increased need for pesticides²⁹.

European Commission Eurostat (Eurostat)

Eurostat is the statistical authority of the EU. The Eurostat is responsible for the coordination, development, production and dissemination of statistics on all sectors including agriculture as well as data on health and safety at work³⁰. This includes collecting data using indicators for health and safety at work such as accidents at work, occupational diseases, work related health problems and accidental injuries and other work-related problems. The Eurostat also has a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) with the DG AGRI, DG EMPL and other Directorates-general to help coordinate their statistical needs and ensure data consistency and quality at EU and national levels.

Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI)

The DG AGRI is the main European Commission department responsible for the EU policy on agriculture and rural development. It also deals with all aspects of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). DG AGRI works to support EU farmers, ensure food security, protect the environment as well as a long-term vision for rural areas through the implementation of several policies designed to ensure sustainable and viable food systems across the EU. The DG Agri's strategic plan sets the objectives for delivering the Commission's priorities for agriculture and rural development effectively. One of the central roles and priorities in the

25 Eurofound also collaborates with ELA and other EU agencies. See <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/home>

26 See <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/about-eurofound/what-we-do>

27 Reports on these are planned for 2023 and 2024

28 See https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/sites/default/files/ef_publication/field_ef_document/ef1384en11.pdf

29 See https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=SDG_13_-_Climate_action

30 See https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/health/database?node_code=hsw

DG Agri's strategic plan is to ensure the adoption and implementation of the new CAP alongside other initiatives and policies like the Green Deal and Farm to Fork Strategy to enable farmers continue the vital work that they do in the EU. There is no direct mention of OSH in agriculture in the DG Agri's 2023-2027 strategic plan document, but the CAP reform included a new Social Conditionality component to ensure OSH in agriculture in Member States. Currently, there is a greater responsibility at national level than at EU level. Through the Social Conditionality mechanism, the new CAP plans to ensure on-farm safety and health in all Member States such that full payment of CAP income support is conditional on whether employers comply with EU social and labour standards and OSH or not. Article 87(1) HzR clearly designates the control system for Social Conditionality as the responsibility of the Member States. It states that '[...] Member States shall make use of their applicable control and enforcement systems in the field of social and employment legislation and applicable labour standards to ensure that beneficiaries [...] comply with the obligations referred to in Annex IV to [SPR]'. The control system for Social Conditionality is designed to rely entirely on the pre-established control mechanisms already in place within the Member States. Article 87(2) HzR, also states: 'Member States shall ensure a clear separation of responsibilities between the authorities or bodies responsible for the enforcement of social and employment legislation and applicable labour standards on the one hand, and the paying agencies on the other, the role of the paying agencies being the execution of payments and the application of penalties under the Social Conditionality mechanism.' This requires communication between the National body responsible for monitoring agricultural health and safety and the payments agency responsible for the administration of the CAP funds. This is much weaker than environmental conditionality, or cross-compliance, with checks against relevant directives and administrative penalties³¹.

"For the first time, receiving CAP income support and rural development funding will be linked to farmers' respect of basic social and labour rights of farm workers, as enshrined in EU laws:

Transparent and predictable employment conditions: Farm workers have to be informed of employment conditions in writing, regardless of the hours worked. This includes place and type of work; beginning and, where relevant, end of employment; information on probation period; paid leave; notice periods; remuneration; work pattern/schedule; and social security (Directive 2019/1152 on transparent and predictable working conditions). On-farm safety and health: Employers must provide adequate risk assessment and risk management provisions to protect workers and ensure the safe and healthy use of farm machinery and equipment (Directives 89/391/EEC and 2009/104/EC Occupational Safety and Health ³²)."

Member States become compliant by 2025 due to the complexity of setting-up systems for the Social Conditionality to work in accordance with the diverse national frameworks in which they operate. Four commenced this practice in 2023 with two more implementing the

³¹https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379383090_Social_conditionality_An_adequate_legal_response_to_challenges_faced_by_agricultural_workers_in_the_EU_or_an_example_of_redwashing_within_the_Common_Agricultural_Policy

³² See https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2021.435.01.0001.01.ENG

Social Conditionality in 2024 and others in 2025³³. Based solely on the strategic framework document of Member States that commenced implementation of the Social Conditionality, it appears that each have set-up different strategies to achieve the requirement of the Social Conditionality. For example, the CAP strategic plan for Austria shows that a sanction system was developed in consultation with social partners. This will be implemented based on principles of equal opportunities and non-discrimination to help farms align with labour laws provisions for the Social Conditionality. The strategic document for Italy sets out to support initiatives that ensure safety and access to essential services for workers while also combatting labour exploitation³⁴. Luxembourg will ensure that payments are only made to farms that comply with provisions of EU labour laws and OSH³⁵ with France also stating that breaches of labour laws will not only attract CAP payment reduction but could also lead to administrative or criminal penalties³⁶. As such, details on how OSH measures will be implemented remains unclear as most Member States are only starting to design and apply the Social Conditionality rule internally and provide OSH advisory services to meet different needs of farms and farm workers. The CAP legislative framework³⁷ seems to take a sectoral approach with OSH incorporated in each agricultural sector. It also stipulates that each Member State's diverse frameworks for OSH should be considered when implementing the requirements for CAP payments. This will ensure that each Member State set unique OSH strategies and programmes to meet farm employers' needs. What this also means is that the agencies responsible for implementing the CAP Social Conditionality for OSH that complies with EU labour laws in the Member States would play significant roles in how successful the Social Conditionality of the CAP will be in ensuring farm OSH at EU level. The responsibility has been passed from DG AGRI to the Member States.

As stipulated in the CAP strategic plan regulation, the national managing authorities and committees in the Member States are responsible for the management and implementation of the CAP. As such, both national managing authorities and committees will play crucial roles in steering farm OSH policies and strategies in Member States. They are also accountable to the European Commission. This also obliges them to provide in-depth information and data on all CAP activities, interventions and beneficiaries for use by the European Commission and other independent analysts and researchers. It is also not clear whether there will be a regional drive among the Member States tailored specifically for farm OSH since implementation is expected to suit each Member State's diverse needs. However, regional farm OSH strategies would be monitored and implemented by their respective regional monitoring committees should that be the case.

33 FR, IT, AT, LU commenced in 2023. ES and PT will start in 2024 and other Member States in 2025

34 At a glance: Italy's CAP Strategic Plan. Overview of key elements and choices defined by Italy in its approved CAP Strategic Plan for the implementation of the CAP 2023-27. Available at:

https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-06/csp-at-a-glance-italy_en.pdf

35 At a glance: Luxembourg's CAP Strategic Plan. Overview of key elements and choices defined by Luxembourg in its approved CAP Strategic Plan for the implementation of the CAP 2023-27. Available at:

https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-04/csp-at-a-glance-luxembourg-en_0.pdf

36 The conditionality of CAP aid: France. Available at: <https://agriculture.gouv.fr/la-conditionnalite-des-aides-pac>

37 See <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32021R2115>

EU CAP Network

To support the new CAP strategic plans, the European CAP Network³⁸ was set up in line with the regulation of the European Parliament to replace the European Network for Rural Development and the EIP-AGRI Network at Union level and the national rural networks. The network takes on the roles of engaging with different stakeholders including organisations, Local Action Groups (LAGs), researchers, practitioners and entrepreneurs in agriculture through knowledge exchange platforms, stakeholder network, capacity building and driving policy while also contributing to the activities of the national CAP networks. The EU CAP network is also tasked with the role of collection, analysis and dissemination of information through a variety of publications on activities implemented under the CAP strategic plans. Several CAP implementation groups have been created as part of the thematic work that the EU CAP Network facilitates. The *“thematic group on CAP strategic plans: towards implementation”* brought together EU level stakeholders, national managing authorities and paying agencies that are involved in the implementation of the CAP strategic programme through the network’s implementation contact point. In terms of farm OSH, the EU CAP network recently published a policy insights document that features *“supporting the health and well-being of Europe’s agricultural workforce”*³⁹ that highlights several policies and programmes that can help improve OSH in agriculture including the uptake of the Social Conditionality of the CAP. In 2024 the CAP Network organised a thematic group on farmer well-being, a workshop and produced a policy brief⁴⁰.

European Food Safety and Authority (EFSA)

The EFSA is an impartial source of scientific advice on risks associated with the EU food chain. The agency belongs to the Network of EU agencies with the likes of EU-OSHA, ELA and Eurofound, but does not have a significant role in OSH in agriculture with the exception of EFSA’s responsibility for producing [guidance](#) on the assessment of exposure of operators, workers etc in a risk assessment of plant protection products. In recent times, there have also been collaboration between EFSA, European Centre for Disease Prevention (ECDC) and the EU-OSHA on *“testing and detection of zoonotic influenza virus infection on humans and occupational safety and health measures for those exposed”*⁴¹. The report depicts how a typical collaboration between EU agencies can provide evidence-based information and guidance to improve farm OSH in the EU.

38 See <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32021R2115>

39 See https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/publications/2023-06/EUCAPNetwork_PolicyInsights_SupportingTheHealthAndWell-beingOfEurope%E2%80%99sAgriculturalWorkforce.pdf

40 See <https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/publications/2024-08/eu-cap-network-good-initiatives-support-mental-health-farmers.pdf>

41 See <https://osha.europa.eu/sites/default/files/Testing-detection-zoonotic-influenza-virus-infections-EU-EEA.pdf>

European Parliament Committees

AGRI (Committee on Agriculture and Rural Development); EMPL (Committee on Employment and Social Affairs); FEMM (Committee on Women’s Rights and Gender Equality)

The European Parliament Committee on Agriculture (AGRI) plays an instrumental role in proposing and approving the establishment of the rules of the CAP, especially the Social Conditionality rules⁴² in the Member States. The AGRI Committee also requests several research reports that inform their legislative decisions including a report on the evaluation of the CAP Strategic Plans and their effective contribution to the achievement of the EU objectives⁴³. The European Parliament Committee on Employment and Social Affairs (EP EMPL) plays the leading role in the EP on all legislative decisions on general OSH issues and should take the lead on defining OSH policies in the agriculture sector. It is the co-legislator and establishes strategic priorities in OSH and working conditions across all sectors, including agriculture. Until now, it has not been active in focusing on the specific needs of the agriculture sector, however it has paid attention recently to the working conditions of seasonal and posted workers in agri-food chains. The European Parliament Committee on Women’s Rights and Gender Equality (FEMM) also continues to support the implementation of the CAP and provided their opinion⁴⁴ for amendments on the proposal for the regulation of the EU Parliament and Council establishing the rules on support for the strategic plans of the CAP. Although the FEMM did not contribute to OSH issues in the CAP, the Committee play an important role in ensuring that provisions for gender mainstreaming, women’s inclusion and equality are considered in the activities of the CAP through gender equality and mainstreaming.

Other Committees

The European Economic and Social Committee and the European Committee of the Regions (EESC)

The European Economic and Social Committee⁴⁵ (EESC) is the voice of organised civil society in Europe. It gives legislative and non-legislative opinions and acts in an advisory capacity to support the European Parliament, Council and Commission either in response to their requests or through its own initiative. It comprises of three groups – employers, workers (but not self-employed workers) and civil society organisations and six sections. Some of the

42 See <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-5841-2021-INIT/en/pdf> for list of directives subject to Social Conditionality

43 See [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2023/747255/IPOL_STU\(2023\)747255_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2023/747255/IPOL_STU(2023)747255_EN.pdf)

44 See https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-8-2019-0200_EN.html#_section9 for their opinion

45 See <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/qe-03-23-244-en-n.pdf>

priorities of the Section for Employment, Social Affairs and Citizenship (SOC)⁴⁶ in 2023 include debates with directors of the European Labour Authority (ELA), Agency for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions (Eurofound) and European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA). The Section on Agriculture, Rural Development and the Environment (NAT) is also responsible for different issues as it pertains to agriculture in the EU including the CAP. In 2023, the EESC NAT commissioned a [study](#) on the working conditions of migrant and seasonal workers in agriculture.

The Committee of Regions (CoR) is also the voice of regions and cities in the EU that represent and advises on new laws that have impact on regions and cities⁴⁷. It is a political assembly that is consulted by the European Commission or through its own initiative on opinions on legislative and policy areas that affect the regions. The Social Policy, Education, Employment, Research and Culture (SEDEC) is working closely with the DG EMPL on various issues. The Commission for Natural Resources (NAT) is also responsible for different issues as it pertains to agriculture in the EU including the CAP. The EESC in collaboration with the CoR also contributed their opinions⁴⁸ on several OSH issues in the EU including the EU strategic framework on health and safety at work 2021-2027. It also contributed its opinion on other issues like guidelines on employment policies of the Member States, precarious work and mental health. The CoR plenary adopted a specific NAT [opinion](#) on “Fair working conditions in agriculture” in 2024.

Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE)

DG SANTE is responsible for EU policies and laws related to food safety, public health, and the health and welfare of animals and crops. Their mission is to protect citizens' health and monitor their food making sure it is safe. As part of this brief DG SANTE is responsible for animal health and wellbeing. The animal welfare lobby is particularly strong. The title of the Commissioner responsible for DG SANTE changed in the last cabinet from The Commissioner for Health and Food Safety to the Commissioner for Health and Animal Welfare. DG SANTE's focus is on public and animal health. This includes the transmission of animal disease to humans from a public health perspective but the specific responsibility for protecting farm and food workers and veterinarians from an occupational health perspective is less clear with responsibilities somehow divided between DG SANTE and DG EMPL.

46 See https://www.eesc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/soc_section_priorities_2023-2025.pdf

47 See <https://cor.europa.eu/en>

48 See <https://dmsearch.eesc.europa.eu/search/opinion> for opinions on OSH in the EU

Social Partners in Agriculture

European Federation of Food, Agriculture, and Tourism Trade Unions (EFFAT)

The EFFAT⁴⁹ works as an organisation of independent and democratic trade unions representing all workers in the Food, Agriculture and other related sectors in the EU. EFFAT is an autonomous European trade union federation. The organisation represents 116 national trade unions from 37 European countries to defend the rights and interests of over 25 million workers including farmers. EFFAT is one of the European Union social partners in agriculture along with GEOPA. Some of the main roles of the EFFAT are to organise, lobby and fight for the rights of the workers that they represent especially in agriculture and contribute to several policies, legislative consultations and social dialogues to improve the working conditions in the agricultural sector. EFFAT also supports several OSH campaigns for the variety of workers in agriculture including migrant and seasonal workers. EFFAT campaigned for, and maintains, a supportive position towards the implementation of the Social Conditionality⁵⁰ of the CAP strategic plans and continue to participate with and work with policy makers and other stakeholders to improve working conditions, safety and health for farmers, most recently on climate change. This as stipulated in EFFAT's action plan for 2022-2023 includes among others, working to improve occupational health and safety⁵¹ as well as promoting the intensification of the ratification ILO Convention 184 in Member States. This also includes improving conditions for small farmers by intensifying the activities of the Small Farmers' Committee. The challenge is that the EU Social Partners model excludes the self-employed.

Committee of Professional Agricultural Organisations (COPA) and the General Confederation of Agricultural Cooperatives (COGECA)

COPA represents over 22 million EU farmers and families. COGECA represents the interests of 22,000 EU agricultural cooperatives⁵² while GEOPA-COPA represents employers of agricultural workers and agricultural workers organisations. Together with the EFFAT, GEOPA-COPA is also an EU social partner in agriculture, and both have signed several European recommendations including on working conditions and the prevention of Musculo-skeletal disorders through consultative negotiations with EU institutions. They

49 European Federation of Food, Agriculture, and Tourism Trade Unions and allied branches

50 EFFAT position on sanctions to be applied in the context of CAP Social Conditionality . Adopted by the EFFAT Executive Committee on 21-22 November 2022. Available at: <https://effat.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/EFFAT-position-on-sanctions-to-be-applied-in-the-context-of-CAP-Social-conditionality.-EN.pdf>

51 EFFAT Action Plan 2022-2023. Available at: <https://effat.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/EN-Action-plan-2022-2023-Final-Victor-02-February-2022.pdf>

52 66 member organisations from the EU Member States

contribute to several EU proposals⁵³ for regulations and directives including the CAP strategic plan and social aspects related to the farm OSH and working conditions of EU farmers. For OSH and other issues pertinent to the agricultural sector, it entails the role of acting as a central network that engages with stakeholders and decision-makers to promote the best interests of EU farmers and employers of agricultural workers.

The European Council of Young Farmers (CEJA)

The European Council of Young Farmers (CEJA) represents the political interests of around two million young farmers from across Europe with members across 22 EU Member states and 33 national member organisations⁵⁴. CEJA acts as a forum for communication and representation between young farmers and European level decision-makers especially in the CAP that works to promote innovation in the agricultural sector through the work that young people do. They do so through advocacy, seminars, visits, conferences, trainings, campaigns and reports on pertinent issues that young people face in agriculture. CEJA also works in partnership with other organisations on several projects including on OSH through the AgriSafetyNet⁵⁵ Erasmus+ project to increase OSH knowledge among farmers and agricultural practitioners and the FARMRes⁵⁶ “Farmers Assistance Resources for Mental Resilience” Erasmus+ project that aims to raise awareness and capacity of farmers to cope with mental health issues. CEJA organised an event on mental wellbeing of young farmers in 2024.

International Stakeholders: International Labour Organisation (ILO), the Food and Agricultural Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) and International Section of the International Social Security Association (ISSA) on Prevention in Agriculture

The ILO⁵⁷ and FAO⁵⁸ both work to promote safer practices and regulations that help reduce occupational hazards, improve OSH and promote decent work standards in the agricultural sector. The International Section of the ISSA on Prevention in Agriculture works to implement accident at work prevention in agriculture through exchange of information, studies that provide in-depth analysis on various aspects of OSH in agriculture⁵⁹.

53 See EFFAT and GEOPA Work Program 2023-2024 of the EU social partners in agriculture available at <https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/cd9afeff-303f-44e8-b7c8-2f88e9a97350/Agri-WP-2023-2024.pdf>

54 See <https://www.ceja.eu/home>

55 See <http://www.agrisafetynet.eu/>

56 See Farmers Assistance Resources for Mental Resilience at <https://farmres.eu>

57 See https://www.ilo.org/safework/info/standards-and-instruments/codes/WCMS_161135/lang--en/index.htm

58 See <https://www.fao.org/rural-employment/work-areas/working-conditions/en/>

59 See <https://ww1.issa.int/prevention-agriculture>

Below is a table compiled by the authors of this deliverable which summarises the key roles and responsibilities of the relevant EU Institutions:

Table 1: Summary of EU Farm Occupational Safety and Health Stakeholders' Roles and Competencies

EU Institutions	OSH Roles	OSH Competencies	Stakeholder
DG AGRI	EU policy on Social Conditionality – working conditions and OSH in agriculture. CAP Policy implementation in Member States.	OSH policy planning and implementation. Oversight on OSH in agriculture in Member States. Focus on improving OSH and working conditions in agriculture through the Social Conditionality.	Implementing and managing
EP AGRI CoMM	Committee responsible for the operation and development of the CAP's Social Conditionality.	Preparation of the reports for legislative proposal on Social Conditionality for OSH in agriculture.	Legislative and implementation monitoring
EP FEMM	Committee responsible for women's rights and gender equality	Contribution the gender issues in the CAP.	Legislative and implementation monitoring
EP EMPL CoMM	Committee responsible for social and employment policy in all sectors (health and safety measures at the workplace)	Employment conditions. Minimum health and safety requirements. Protection of workers Wages and gender equality.	Legislative and implementation monitoring
EU CAP Network	Support for the implementation of the CAP Social Conditionality plans	Knowledge exchange. Monitoring and implementation of the CAP.	Information Networking
DG EMPL	Implementation and enforcement of the EU working conditions and OSH legislation. Policy development, guidance, coordination and governance	Oversight. OSH Legislation. OSH management. Consultation. Enforcement and inspection oversight.	Legislative and implementation monitoring

EU-OSHA – European Agency for Safety and Health at Work	European Union information and guidance agency for occupational safety and health	Support and guidance for OSH issues. OSH risks assessment and survey. Collaborative online encyclopaedia on OSH. OSH campaigns. OSH risks prevention. OSH research.	Policy support and information
Advisory Committee on OSH (ACSH)	Assists the European Commission in the preparation, implementation and evaluation of OSH activities. Facilitates cooperation between national administrations, trade unions and employers' organisations.	Identify OSH policy priorities. Exchange of views and experiences between Member States and stakeholders across the EU. Connecting interest groups. Working parties (WPs) on specific technical OSH issues.	Support and information
Senior Labour Inspectors Committee (SLIC)	Provide opinion on all problems relating to the enforcement of OSH community law in Member States.	Exchange of information among national bodies. OSH inspection and reporting.	Labour inspection
DG Eurostat	Agriculture, fisheries and OSH statistics and data in Europe.	Data and analysis. Lead harmonization of statistics in collaboration with national statistical authorities. Communication and Dissemination.	Statistics
European Labour Authority (ELA)	Strengthen fair and effective mobility across the EU. Coordination of social security systems.	Information exchange and cooperation. Joint inspections. Analyses and risk assessment. Tackling undeclared work. Capacity building for labour mobility. Seasonal	Information, labour mobility

		and posted workers. Cooperation with EU-OSHA.	
Eurofound – European Foundation for Living and Working Conditions	Provides information, advice and expertise on working conditions. Support for OSH EU institutions, agencies and social partners	Research and analyses. Pan-European surveys. Monitoring and analysing developments in industrial relations and social dialogues. Collaboration with EU-OSHA.	Knowledge and information
European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)	Advice and communication on food safety, animal and plant health risks in the food chain.	Scientific knowledge and expertise on public health risks related to the food chain.	Risk assessment, knowledge, information and collaboration
EFFAT	Protect and improve workers’ rights and employment conditions.	Monitor implementation of Social Conditionality in the Member States. Improving working conditions for mobile workers and small farmers. Improving occupational health and safety.	Lobby/social
COPA-COGECA	Represent the employers of agricultural workers, agricultural cooperatives and agricultural worker organisations to promote employers’ specific social interests. Present opinions on proposals for Regulations and Directives governing social policy.	Member Sectoral Social Dialogue Committee led by DG EMPL. Negotiate collective labour agreements at national level. Improving occupational health and safety.	Lobby/social

CEJA	Forum for communication between young farmers and decision makers.	Policy and advocacy. Campaigns and communication.	Information
ILO (International Labour organisation)	OSH and labour standards. OSH information. International labour standards	Labour inspection standards. Safety and health Convention C184 and Recommendation R192. Codes of practice for OSH in agriculture and decent work guidelines in agriculture.	International policy guidance
FAO	Promote safer OSH practices in agriculture	Inform policy. Technical support. Contributes to improving decent work in agriculture.	Policy and information
ISSA – Agriculture Section (International Social Security Association)	Social security administration	Expert knowledge and guidance. Studies and research. Collaboration and technical advice. Dissemination.	Preventive actions and guidance.
EESC – European Economic and Social Committee	Represent civil society, trade unions and employers' organisations.	Opinions on legislative and non-legislative issues in both agriculture and social issues.	
CoR – European Committee of the Regions	Represent local and regional government.	Opinions on legislative and non-legislative issues in both agriculture and social issues.	

SOURCE: AUTHORS' COMPILATION BASED ON STAKEHOLDERS' REPORTS, STRATEGIC DOCUMENTS, WEBSITE INFORMATION AND ACTION PLANS.

Analysing Stakeholder Connections for Farm OSH

Occupational safety and health in agriculture in the EU is multifaceted. The responsibility to adhere to occupational safety and health regulations lies with farmers, farm employees and employers under the oversight and enforcement by national government bodies. However, how each stakeholder works, their roles and the nature of connections, influence and interest that they can foster remain crucial for supporting farm OSH. Based on their roles, the stakeholders described in the previous section fall under three main categories – oversight, support and social/representation. **Oversight stakeholders** are the main decision and policy makers backed by EU legislative power. They include the EU institutions DG EMPL and DG AGRI that provide oversight on employment, agriculture and rural development in the EU. They also include the advisory committee on OSH and Senior Labour Inspectors Committee that provide advice and reports on OSH inspections at EU level. The European Parliament’s Committee on Agriculture (EP AGRI), European Parliament Committee on Employment and Social Affairs (EP EMPL) and European Parliament Committee on Women’s Rights and Gender Equality (EP FEMM) also contribute to labour, OSH and gender issues at EU Parliamentary level.

OSH **support stakeholders** provide information or implementation advice depending on their mandates. The EU-OSHA is well positioned as a support agency under the DG EMPL that provides information on OSH using a variety of tools and information on the framework directive⁶⁰ and other 24 EU directives that set the minimum requirements for OSH as it relates to agriculture. The DG EMPL also operates through the ELA and Eurofound to provide information, data and guidance on labour and working conditions across all sectors. The introduction of Social Conditionality did not come through the usual OSH route, and it is unclear how DG AGRI plans to work with these agencies to situate farm OSH in their work. The Eurostat and Eurofound also act as support stakeholders that provide data and information on OSH in agriculture on accidents, risks and work-related diseases as well as working conditions. **Social/representation stakeholders** represent farmers, farm employees and employers and give opinions on OSH. They are crucial for reaching out and connecting stakeholders interested in agriculture. They include the three EU social partners in agriculture EFFAT, COPA-COGECA (including GEOPA) and CEJA that represent the interests of farmers, workers in agriculture, farm employers and young farmers respectively. While EFFAT and GEOPA work together on their joint programme to ensure health and safety for those that they represent, it is not clear how they work with the CEJA to include OSH as it pertains to young farmers. Also, the EESC represents civil society including farmers organisations, civil society and trade unions and the CoR represents regions and local authorities in the EU, and both have contributed with opinions and studies on OSH issues in agriculture.

All three categories of OSH stakeholders share information on OSH in agriculture and have varying degrees of power to influence farm OSH output at the EU level through their collaborations. However, it could mean that some of these collaborations are done with only familiar collaborative silos since there is no platform or forum that brings all stakeholders together on OSH issues in agriculture. Some of these stakeholders especially the agencies

60 See <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A31989L0391&qid=1615985898418>

under DG EMPL have worked together and continue to do so on various aspects of OSH in agriculture. For example, a recent study⁶¹ done by SLIC in collaboration with the EU-OSHA shows that agriculture is still among the high-risk sectors in the EU facing new, emerging and traditional OSH risks. The study highlights temporary, permanent and self-employed workers exposed to risks. However, other at-risk groups such as young and disabled people as well as women and older people that could potentially give a different insight into the nature of risk that workers face were not shown. While studies like this show the outcome of stakeholder collaboration on OSH issues, it also shows the need for sector-specific (in this case agriculture) cooperation that targets OSH in agriculture.

The introduction of the Social Conditionality for working conditions and on-farm OSH have gained the attention of stakeholders at the EU level. This includes among others legislative contributions from EP EMPL, EP FEMM and EP AGRI as well as the opinions and positions of EESC, CoR, EFFAT and COPA-COGECA. However, it is not clear how these collaborations will influence successful implementation of the Social Conditionality. The expertise of OSH stakeholders will be needed to help Member States to develop the systems needed to overcome complexities and successfully implement sustainable OSH practices.

Conclusions of the scoping review

Several EU institutions and stakeholders contribute to improve OSH in agriculture in the EU. There is a need for an **OSH in agriculture monitoring system** for both farmers, farm workers and employers and OSH stakeholders. This presents a great opportunity to develop and implement strategic plans that are tailored to meet the farm OSH needs that are peculiar to them. How key performance indicators are measured and monitored needs to be considered to avoid issues with harmonising key performance indicators at national levels. Because the data collected by Eurofound and Eurostat are sector-based and as result of the collaboration with the EU-OSHA, a collaboration with other stakeholders to develop key performance indicators that capture both OSH successes and infringement encountered in the farm would improve prospects for monitoring OSH. The new CAP's drive for gender equality and generational renewal to increase women and younger people's participation in agriculture presents opportunities for inclusiveness and farm business sustainability but also presents new challenges and risks for farm OSH that needs to be considered as Member States implement farm OSH strategies.

It also underpins the need for **continuous collaboration between stakeholders through an OSH stakeholder forum**, the use of reliable OSH data and the implementation of OSH measures at the EU and national levels to achieve OSH objectives under the Social Conditionality of the CAP and the EU Strategic Framework on Health and Safety at work. Together, these stakeholders constitute a complex web of actors that have the capacity to pool their expertise to improve OSH in agriculture. There is also a need for all OSH stakeholders to **integrate farm OSH into programmes and projects**, as well as their annual action plans. Also, in line with the European Economic and Social Committee's

61 See <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/fea534f4-2590-4490-bca6-504782b47c79/library/3bad8ad7-c7d9-4f1b-af38-43404cd7d859/details>

opinion⁶² on the Health and Safety at Work – EU Strategic Framework, there is need for **evidence-based initiatives** to help guarantee safe and healthy work environments among self-employed farmers and farms operated by families.

Interviews and focus groups

To complement the mapping exercise, interviews and focus groups were conducted to assess current policy design and delivery and make recommendations for improved policy frameworks at the right level of governance considering the various competencies involved. The object is to consider how to strengthen policy design and delivery at the EU level addressing farmer health and safety. The intention is to make recommendations to improve policy frameworks at the level of EU governance being mindful of the various competencies involved. Three SafeHabitus events that dealt with governance were treated as focus groups and eight interviews were conducted with representatives from EU-OSHA, DG AGRI, DG EMPL, Eurofound, EFFAT, GEOPA, a Senior Labour Inspector and the EESC. Six interviews were in person and two were by zoom. All interviewees signed consent forms to be interviewed, and seven gave permission for the interviews to be recorded. DG Sante twice declined an invitation for interview.

The key findings underline that when directives, regulations and policy exist relating to farmer health and safety, they relate to paid farm *employees* and not *self-employed* farmers or their families. Policy makers and stakeholders are aware that this excludes most people working on farms, 86% of the 8,700,000 farmers and farm workers in the EU⁶³. Policy makers and stakeholders feel constrained in their ability to tackle health and safety for self-employed farm workers because it is beyond their remit. Policy makers and stakeholders also felt that the lack of robust evidence about farm accidents for the self-employed means it is not a priority. Available data on farm injuries and fatalities is inconsistent across Member States. It is gathered in different ways and there is significant underreporting. This lack of data can make farmer health and safety seem less of a pressing policy issue than the reality suggests. People interviewed had mixed views on Social Conditionality. On the one hand it is a very positive development to protect the rights of seasonal workers who are a vulnerable group in agriculture. However other policy makers and stakeholders were concerned that it has limited powers to successfully address health and safety concerns. How to progress change and improve policy frameworks is a difficult question. Policies to address the health and safety of seasonal workers are a high priority. This is less so for self-employed workers and policy makers feel their capacities are limited. Below the key findings are elaborated. Following that, some suggested recommendations are made that might advance policies and governance of farmer health and safety.

62 See <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/en/our-work/opinions-information-reports/opinions/health-safety-work-eu-strategic-framework-2021-2027>

63 See https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Farmers_and_the_agricultural_labour_force_-_statistics

Governance and available data on farmer health and safety

While all mentioned data, the EESC and the Senior Labour Inspector particularly emphasised that unreliable EU data on farm accidents and fatalities impacts on policy design because of a lack of understanding of the issue. The requirements for reporting differ between countries. SafeHabitus research found that only 13 of the 27 EU member states report occupational injuries and fatalities of self-employed farmers and family workers. This means that Eurostat data on self-employed farmers and family workers are underreported. In some countries the self-employed are not required to report injuries or fatalities. In other countries (Ireland) this issue has been surmounted by classifying self-employed workers as their own employee. This legally obliges the reporting of accidents and fatalities. In some countries fatalities and accidents that occur outside of the Eurostat working age of 15-64 years do not need to be reported. This omits two groups particularly vulnerable to farm accidents: young people and older people. A number of interviewees reported that the lack of accurate data means the health and safety issues on farms are not the policy priority they ought to be. It also leads to a misunderstanding of farming safety across Europe. Countries with robust reporting mechanisms seem to have more accidents and fatalities, while in fact their figures are likely to be more accurate reflections of farm accidents and fatalities in Europe.

Policy, governance and self-employed farmers and farm family workers

86% of farm workers are self-employed or family workers. This group are absent from the remit of all the directorates and agencies interviewed. Social Conditionality, was introduced in the current CAP and is the responsibility of DG AGRI. It is outlined in Article 14 of Regulation 2021/2115. It aims to improve employment conditions for people in agriculture and focuses on transparent working conditions, contracts, health and safety and correct use of work equipment. However, Social Conditionality only applies to farm employees. The health, safety and correct use of work equipment is not developed in a way to benefit self-employed farmers and family workers.

EU-OSHA collects data on health and safety for different occupations, deal with intermediaries around reducing risk, and run extensive campaigns. Their remit on the whole mainly applies to employees, and not self-employed workers (with a few exceptions such as in the construction sector⁶⁴). They recognise that farming is an at-risk occupational sector. They also recognise that self-employed workers are an 'overlooked group'. One reason they think agriculture has not arisen as a priority in the past is that the Member State labour inspectorate does not have agriculture in their remit. Agriculture is seen as a 'difficult' occupation in terms of health and safety because of the percentage of self-employed. The status of seasonal workers is the key priority for the directorates and agencies working with agriculture.

64 The [EU-OSHA Directive](#) on temporary or mobile construction sites incorporates OSH measures mutatis mutandis for the self-employed

DG EMPL are responsible for the health and safety of the EU workforce. However, again, their responsibility is to on the whole, mainly to employees in the same way as EU-OSHA. They say that the way the Framework Directive and individual Directives around health and safety are written mean that this must be the focus. While they are aware of the high percentage of self-employed farmers and the risks of the occupation, they said that it is not that 'they don't care' but it is how the treaties are drafted. They note that Member States can go further than EU requirements and point to how Ireland have done so by making self-employed workers their own employees.

The Social Dialogue on Agriculture was established in 1999. It is a tripartite agreement between workers, employees and civil society. The workers are represented by EFFAT and the employees by GEOPA, the representative body of EU farm employers. Their focus includes accident prevention and taking particular account of musculoskeletal disorders. The way in which the social partners are defined however means that self-employed workers do not have a voice in this dialogue.

Self-employed farmers and their families are not covered by the relevant EU directorates and agencies. The view of policy makers and agencies is that nothing can be done about this omission because of their self-employed status, and this is beyond their remit.

EU Coordination

There are many EU directorates and agencies that have a role in farm safety and wellbeing. Eurofound undertake research and provide data on improving working and living conditions in Europe. DG EMPL, and in particular their Health and Safety Unit, have overarching responsibility for occupational health and safety of workers. DG AGRI, through Social Conditionality, now has a responsibility for farm workers health, well-being and working conditions. The EU OSH (occupational safety and health) Agency has responsibility for collecting data, developing tools such as online risk assessments, and raising awareness. GEOPA and EFFAT, along with the European Economic and Social Committee, have a Social Dialogue on Agriculture, where farm worker safety has recently come to the fore. DG SANTE have responsibility for public health and animal health and welfare. It is not clear whether this responsibility stretches to farm workers, who may contract diseases from animals. All of these bodies only deal with farm employees, missing out on the majority of self-employed farmers and the work of their families. In general, as well as being limited in its scope, policy makers and agencies report limited coordination between the different directorates and agencies. EU-OSHA does not work closely with DG SANTE or DG AGRI. They work more closely with the European Centre for Disease Control (ECDC) and the European Labour Authority (ELA). They work with ECDC to highlight that human infections from animals are more of an occupational health concern than a public health issue; in other words, it is mostly (farm) workers and veterinarians who suffer these infections from animals than the general public. OSHA noted that Covid was very important in distinguishing between occupational health and general public health; for example, when transport reopened, the main concern was for public health, while OSHA were able to highlight that employers also had responsibility to the workers who were employees in the tourism and transport sectors. They work with the ELA on campaigns on seasonal workers. EFFAT reported having much more influence on social policy through the Social Dialogue than through interactions with directorates. EFFAT and GEOPA both noted that they are collaborating closely on climate change and have issued

a joint statement on the need for more work on the impact of climate change on the health, safety and wellbeing of farm employees and farm employers. DG EMPL prepared a draft of the individual Directive for the Agriculture sector in the 1990s (as stipulated in the Annex to the Framework Directive) but it was never adopted owing to lack of agreement between the social partners. DG EMPL consider it too complex because of the high percentage of self-employed workers. They have had one on construction, and the construction directive covers self-employed workers as well as employees. DG AGRI sees health and safety as the responsibility of DG EMPL. They reported a lack of appetite for Social Conditionality amongst surveyed farmers. It is seen as increasing the administrative burden, which is something DG AGRI is committed to reducing in their policies. Eurofound expressed an interest in doing further work on farmer working conditions, particularly in relation to climate change. Their work programme is decided by their stakeholders, and they need someone to advocate for agriculture. They have had agricultural stakeholders in the past, but they did not push for research. Their recent report on job quality and climate change (Eurofound, 2024) provides interesting observations on the climate change impact on farmers. It is interesting to note that they refer to self-employed farmers rather than farm employees.

There is a sense from policy makers and agencies that there is fractured responsibility and oversight of farmer health and safety. It is seen as the responsibility of other directorates and agencies. Policy makers and agencies are constrained in their ability to consider issues for self-employed farmers and their families, citing their remit as only relating to farm employees. Where there is focused concern, it is on seasonal and migrant workers. Social Conditionality, while lauded as tackling farmer health and safety, mainly focuses on seasonal and migrant workers (while still excluding key sectors such as horticulture, wine and olive sectors), and health and safety is only one component of Social Conditionality. Within DG EMPL, seasonal and migrant workers are not under the remit of the Health and Safety Unit, rather they have their own Unit. This is seen as necessary because issues such as undeclared work and housing are other components that need to be addressed. Policy makers and agencies reported little coordination between directorates and agencies at the EU level.

Policy framework and EU actor roles in Social Conditionality

In all of the interviews undertaken, there were lengthy conversations about the policy and governance of Social Conditionality. EFFAT has long championed the need to address exploited conditions of some agricultural workers, particularly migrant and seasonal workers both within the EU and third countries. They often do not have contracts, have dangerous working conditions, low pay and long hours, inadequate housing and are vulnerable to accidents and illness⁶⁵. In the current CAP framework, the EU has included a commitment to 'Social Conditionality'. It is a complex mechanism with multiple legal requirements⁶⁶. It applies to employers who employ more than ten workers. It sets out that

65 European Federation of Food Agriculture and Tourism Trade Unions, 'EFFAT's Demands in View of the Post-2020 CAP Revision. A Social CAP for Achieving Fair Work in European Agriculture', [see https://effat.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/EFFATs-Demands-in-view-of-the-post-2020-CAP-Revision-EN-1-1.pdf](https://effat.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/EFFATs-Demands-in-view-of-the-post-2020-CAP-Revision-EN-1-1.pdf)

66 Bangsgaard Lyngs, T. 2024. Social Conditionality : An adequate legal response to challenges faced by agricultural workers in the EU, or an example of red washing within the Common Agricultural Policy? *European Labour Law Journal* 15(4) 773–785

they must ensure that their workers have transparent and predictable working conditions, introduce measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work, and provide for the minimum safety and health requirements for the use of work equipment by workers at work. If farm employers are found to breach these conditions, then they can have CAP payments reduced. It was agreed very late in the negotiations of the CAP framework. Abuse of migrant workers received considerable media coverage during Covid-19. The Socialist Group were very strong in the Parliament during the negotiations and advocated for Social Conditionality. During the interviews various perspectives on Social Conditionality emerged, and there was general agreement that it is problematic to enforce.

The implementation of Social Conditionality is the responsibility of the Member States. It relies on their existing enforcement measures, and on inspectors to inform the national CAP payments agency if a breach in behaviour is found. The former Health and Safety inspector, DG AGRI, DG EMPL and GEOPA people interviewed all agreed that this leads to a situation which is 'not a level playing field'. In some countries inspections are required, in others it is not compulsory for farms to be inspected. The interviewees noted and recognised that this means that in one EU country then a farmer could be penalised for behaviour while a farmer in another country is not penalised for the same behaviour. Interviewees noted that this leads to inequalities for farmers, with some being penalised and fined at the national level (a double penalty) while there is no penalty in a different context. Health and safety inspections at a national level are not always adequate and often underfunded⁶⁷. Often health and safety inspectors are not trained in agricultural health and safety. There is no change in the existing enforcement rules, they simply rely on what already exists at the national level. Interviewees noted that Social Conditionality was as effective as 'Member State enforcement'.

There are shortcomings of the Social Conditionality measure. The one that interviewees spoke most about is that the horticulture sector is where most abuse of agricultural workers occurs. Yet interviewees noted that this sector receives support differently and does not receive direct payments in the usual way so they cannot be penalised by the terms of Social Conditionality⁶⁸. This limits the governance framework. Interviewees discussed how Social Conditionality came late in the negotiations and was rushed. It was noted that it was seen as a political victory for the Socialist Group who knew it had 'little teeth'. DG AGRI reported that this places them in a difficult position by trying to convert it into effective measures. DG EMPL noted that Social Conditionality did not come through OSH in the usual way of health and safety measures. Usually there are long negotiations between employers, employees and Member States. The longer process and tripartite agreements mean measures are more likely to be effective.

There was uncertainty about whether Social Conditionality will remain in the next CAP Framework. DG AGRI noted that farmers do not want to implement it, and DG AGRI note the

67 See <https://www.euractiv.com/section/agriculture-food/news/commission-admits-weaknesses-of-farm-funds-social-pillar/>

68 See <https://www.euractiv.com/section/agriculture-food/news/commission-admits-weaknesses-of-farm-funds-social-pillar/>

administrative burden it creates, which they are committed to reduce. EFFAT dispute the administrative burden argument. GEOPA are opposed to Social Conditionality. The timing was seen as unfortunate, coming with farmer protests and the rise in energy and fertilizer costs. Social Conditionality only became mandatory in 2025, and until that point only six countries had voluntarily undertaken implementation of the measure.

All the policy makers and agencies interviewed recognised that farming is a dangerous occupation involving animals, machinery, chemicals and climate change. They also acknowledged that Social Conditionality does not address any of the health and safety issues relating to 86% of agricultural workers, the self-employed and their families. At a policy level there is limited capacity to address the needs of this group. The self-employed status is seen as too difficult. DG EMPL have never had a Directive on agriculture, saying the percentage of self-employed makes it too difficult. There was however a Directive on construction, which also has many self-employed workers and a draft Directive on Agriculture did circulate at some stage in the 1990s but did not advance any further than a draft. DG EMPL offer guidance for agriculture and set up a separate unit to deal with seasonal workers. It is clear that seasonal workers are the main focus. DG AGRI repeated that Social Conditionality only relates to employees and they have no remit to deal with self-employed workers. EU-OSHA agree that the self-employed are overlooked when it comes to health and safety, even though they face the same risks as employees.

Policy framework and women

There was a lack of general awareness regarding health and safety risks for women in agriculture. EU-OSHA concurred that more efforts could be directed towards addressing the needs of women in this sector. Although EFFAT have focussed somewhat on this issue, they recognize the necessity for increased attention. Across the various Directorates, there was limited knowledge or emphasis on gender-specific concerns in the context of agriculture, health, and safety

Conclusions

The interviews show a number of issues that need to be addressed around farmer health and safety. The first is that policy makers believe the lack of accurate data is problematic. Farmer health and safety is less of a social policy priority than it needs to be because of the under reporting of accidents and fatalities. Until accurate data is generated, it will remain a struggle to bring farmer health and safety to the forefront as a policy priority.

Interviewees reported a lack of coordination between the relevant directorates and agencies. However, the social partners on agriculture, EFFAT and GEOPA, reported a close working relationship and have issued a joint statement together on the implications for workers and employees of climate change. GEOPA work closely with agriculture. EU-OSHA does not work closely with DG AGRI, or DG SANTE. Clear demarcations were drawn around directorate and agency responsibilities during the interviews.

The single biggest difficulty is that what legislation exists, it only relates to contracted workers. This excludes 86% of agricultural workers. When this is raised, the issue is acknowledged, but at a governance level it is not the responsibility of the relevant DGs, or

agencies interviewed. The focus is very much on seasonal workers, given the high-profile coverage in the media about violations of working conditions, living arrangements and in some cases, slave like arrangements. However, similar questions should be asked about the conditions of self-employed workers. For this project, five interviews were undertaken with survivors of farm accidents, people who lost limbs or are wheelchair users. Three of these reported working eighteen-hour days when their accidents occurred. They discussed the extreme stress they were under because of their working conditions. They talked about undertaking work in poor weather conditions because it needed to be done, and they could not ask an employee in those conditions. The demands of agriculture, the financial returns, and the amount of bureaucracy and its impact on self-employed workers and their families, needs attention in agricultural policy.

The hopes and expectations that Social Conditionality will address issues of health and safety in agriculture are curtailed. They do not consider self-employed farmers. It is reliant on existing inspection and regulation arrangements in Member States which differ considerably and are often inadequate. The penalty imposed by withholding direct payments is not relevant for the horticultural sector, which is where most violations of seasonal workers rights occur. It will be interesting to note if there are any examples of withholding CAP payments in the six countries that implemented Social Conditionality before it became mandatory. While Social Conditionality is seen as a progressive development, the views of the interviewees is that it needs to be better designed and governed.

It is not clear which body is best placed to achieve change. The directorates and agencies are limited in their ability to address the issue of self-employed farmers. The main farming lobby group, COPA-COGECA, is opposed to any regulations on self-employed farmers and does not champion health and safety as a primary concern. One interviewee commented that farm animal welfare is better regulated than farmer welfare because there are so many animal welfare lobby groups. Research has shown that lobby groups have a powerful influence on EU policy⁶⁹. If accurate robust data becomes available, it may then have to become a priority for the relevant directorates. In the meantime, there is scope for COPA- COGECA to use its lobby group powers to champion the need for greater policy attention to the health and safety of farm workers.

69 See <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/soru.12475>

Recommendations

Improve policy governance for farm OSH at the EU level

- **DG EMPL:** DG EMPL should take responsibility for coordinating a cross-DG/agency working group on farm OSH. Given that it is recognised by EU policy makers that there is little coordination between bodies, this will not happen until one entity takes responsibility for coordination.
- **DG EMPL:** As originally foreseen in the Framework Directive, DG EMPL should undertake a Directive on Agriculture. This should include self-employed workers. This would provide an in-depth and wide-ranging overview of the OSH needs of all farm workers including the self-employed. It could also provide an overview of the regulatory and legislative changes required at an EU level to ensure all relevant bodies have responsibility for self-employed farm workers in their remit. It should also include an in-depth study of the needs of pregnant women regarding contact with animals and pesticides.
- **Member States** should ratify the ILO Convention C184 on OSH in Agriculture and implement the measures of its supplementary Recommendation 192 (which includes the self-employed). This convention, if adopted by all Member States along with the measures of its supplementary Recommendation 192, would de facto serve as a European Directive on OSH and working conditions in agriculture. A similar approach has been successfully taken up by the EU Council of Ministers and EU Social Partners in the fisheries sector.
- **EFFAT, GEOPA, COPA-COGECA, CEJA:** Until regulatory change happens the social partners will continue to be EFFAT and GEOPA, omitting self-employed workers. Before this is achieved, EFFAT and GEOPA should work closely with COPA-COGECA and CEJA to ensure representation of self-employed farm workers. GEOPA and EFFAT hope to develop an insurance scheme that will compensate farm employers and employees for lost income due to climate change. They intend to use the Parity Funds at their disposal to avoid private insurance that will charge high premiums. It is essential that such an insurance scheme is also inclusive of self-employed farmers.
- **COPA-COGECA** should use its lobbying power to raise the need for health and safety of self-employed workers to be an EU policy priority.

Improve quality data about farm accidents to ensure farm OSH is a policy priority:

- **DG EMPL** should undertake a directive on OSH in agriculture that should address the issue of standardising inspection practices and requirements across the Member States. This can be implemented by the European Labour Authority and the EU SLIC (Senior Labour Inspectors' Committee) and would both improve the quality of information, and level an unfair playing field that currently exists; at present some Member States carry out compulsory farm inspections, while in other Member States, farm inspection of self-employed farmers is not compulsory.
- To improve the quality, consistency, and comparability of data on farm-related fatalities—including deaths by suicide—Eurostat should establish a dedicated

working group on coronial and medico-legal death data. This group should bring together representatives from national statistical offices, coroners' services, public health authorities, and relevant agricultural and labour bodies. The working group should:

- Focus specifically on improving the classification, recording, and reporting of unnatural deaths in the agricultural sector, including suicides among farmers and farm family members.
 - Identify best practices and common standards for collecting and coding coronial data across Member States, considering the unique circumstances of farm-related deaths.
 - Develop guidelines to support more granular, sector-specific analysis of mortality data in agriculture, and ensure that this information feeds into EU-level health, safety, and social sustainability indicators.
 - This initiative should be aligned with ongoing efforts under the Farm Sustainability Data Network and supported by the European Commission in coordination with relevant DGs, including DG EMPL, DG AGRI, and DG SANTE.
- DG EMPL/ EU-OSHA/ DG SANTE/ Eurofound: More data is needed on the risks posed by pesticides and animal disease to pregnant and breastfeeding women. More data in general is needed about health and safety risks for women.

Governance of Social Conditionality:

- **DG EMPL and DG AGRI:** Social Conditionality should be DG EMPL's responsibility as the responsible DG for labour conditions and worker health and safety. Social Conditionality should be revised as part of a Directive on Agriculture undertaken by DG EMPL. Until this happens, DG EMPL and DG AGRI should coordinate more effectively on their policies. DG AGRI should consider its role in ensuring implementation of Social Conditionality by implementing similar measures to cross-compliance.

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